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A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE HUMAN BODY

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ABSTRACT

Information about the innate and acquired immunity of vitamin D in the human body. Currently, vitamin D deficiency is very common in our republic. It also talks about the role of vitamin D in skin photoprotection, as well as how vitamin D is used for preventive and therapeutic purposes in infectious diseases and oncology, which leads to a decrease in cancer progression. The issue of adequate provision of vitamin D during pregnancy is of particular importance, since adequate nutrition of the fetus with vitamin D during pregnancy plays an important role in its good formation and prevention of a number of diseases. In addition, daily or weekly intake of vitamin D leads to a decrease in the incidence of acute respiratory infections. It is noted that it is important to know the initial level of vitamin D in patients when taking this supplement.

Keywords: vitamin D, vitamin D deficiency, children, doses, cancer, photoprotection, autism.

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НОВАЯ ТОЧКА ЗРЕНИЯ НА РОЛЬ ВИТАМИНА D В ОРГАНИЗМЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Информация о врожденном и приобретенном иммунитете к витамину D в организме человека. В настоящее время дефицит витамина D очень распространен в нашей республике. В нем также рассказывается о роли витамина D в фотозащите кожи, а также о том, как витамин D

используется в профилактических и терапевтических целях при инфекционных заболеваниях и онкологии, что приводит к снижению прогрессирования рака. Вопрос адекватного обеспечения витамином D во время беременности имеет особое значение, поскольку адекватное питание плода витамином D во время беременности играет важную роль в его хорошем формировании и профилактике ряда заболеваний. Кроме того, ежедневный или еженедельный прием витамина D приводит к снижению заболеваемости острыми респираторными инфекциями.

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D VITAMINING INSON TANASIDAGI ROLIGA YANGI NUQTAI NAZAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Vitamin D ning inson organizmida tugʻma va orttirilgan immuniteti haqida. Xozirgi vaqtda respublikamizda vitamin D etishmovchiligi juda koʻp qayd etilmoqda. D vitamini terining fotoximoyasida qanday rol oʻynashi haqida, shuningdek, vitamin D yuqumli kasalliklar va onkologiya uchun profilaktika va davolash maqsadlarida xam ishlatilishi yoritilgan, bu esa saraton rivojlanishining pasayishiga olib keladi. Homiladorlik paytida D vitamini bilan etarli darajada taʼminlash masalasi alohida ahamiyatga ega, chunki xomiladorlik vaqtida xomila vitamin D bilan etarli darajada taminlanishi uning yaxshi rovojlanishida va bir qator kasalliklarning paydo boʻlishini oldini olishda katta rol oʻynaydi. Shuningdek, D vitaminini har kuni yoki haftada qabul qilish oʻtkir respiratorli infektsiyalar bilan kasallanishning pasayishiga olib keladi. Ushbu qoʻshimchani qabul qilishda bemorlarda D vitaminining boshlangʻich darajasini bilish muhimligi qayd etilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: D vitamini, D vitamini yetishmovchiligi, bolalar, dozalar, saraton, fotoximoya, autism

Kirish. D vitamini haqida zamonaviy maʼlumotlar va ushbu vitamin yetishmovchiligida kelib chiqadigan kasalliklarni oʻrganish

Tadqiqot usullari. Zamonaviy adabiy maʼlumotlarni tahlil qilish.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Oʻzbekistonda bir qator tadqiqotlar oʻtkazildi, ularning natijalari dunyo maʼlumotlariga mos keladi va odamlarda D vitaminining past darajasi keng tarqalganligini tasdiqlaydi. Ushbu tadqiqotlar natijalariga koʻra, barcha yoshdagi aholining 90% da D vitamini tanqisligi (< 20 ng/ml), 8 % da D vitamini yetishmovchiligi (20-30 ng/ml), qolgan 2% esa normal vitamin miqdori mavjud (30-100 ng / ml). Shuni takidlash kerakki 1 yoshgacha boʻlgan bolalarning organizmdagi vitamin D miqdorini bilish juda muxumdur chunki $> 50\%$ bolalar raxitdan aziyat chekmoqdalar. Afsuski, bunday vaziyatga qaramay, bolalar shifokori hali ham D vitaminini faqat 1 yoshgacha boʻlgan bolalarga buyuradilar [3]. Bugungi kunda inson tanasida D vitaminining yetarli va yetarli emasligi haqidagi pozitsiya qayta koʻrib chiqilgan.

Koʻpgina yevropalik mutaxassislarining fikriga koʻra, D vitamini 25 (OH) D darajasi sifatida aniqlanadi 20 ng/ml dan kam boʻlsa D vitamini gipovitaminozi, 10 ng/ml dan kam D vitamini yetishmovchiligi, chegara yetishmovchiligi atigi 21-29 ng/ml ni tashkil qiladi va optimal D vitamini tarkibi 30-100 ng / ml ni tashkil qiladi. Shuni taʼkidlash kerakki, quyoshli xavoda juda kam sayr qilish va uyda uzoq vaqt qolish quyosh nurlari taʼsirida terida D vitamini sintezining sezilarli darajada kamayayishiga olib keladi [7-9]. Agar odam quyoshli havoda yursa ham, quyosh kremi va kiyim-kechak, shahardagi tutun yoki chang atmosferasida bu doza kamayadi. Noqulay faktorlar kombinatsiyasi (ultrabinafsha nurlarining yetishmovchilik intensivligi, teri rangining qoraligi, yuqori

bulutlilik, tutun, quyoshdan himoya qiluvchi kremlardan foydalanish va boshqalar) ta'siri quyosh nuri orqali terida vitamin D sintez qilish miqdorini sezilarli darajada kamayishiga olib keladi. Ammo shuni takidlash kerakki, endogen D vitamini yetishmovchiligi kuzatilsa surunkali ichak kasalliklari, surunkali jigar kasalliklari, buyrak yetishmovchiligi, malabsorbsiya sindromi, xolestaz, shuningdek, a-gidroksilaza faolligining genetik jihatdan pasayishi va ovqat hazm qilish tizimining yetuk emasligi kabi kasalliklarga olib kelishi mumkin. D vitamini nima ekanligi haqida hali ham faol munozaralar mavjud: steroid gormonmi yoki vitaminmi. Gap shundaki, vitaminlar antioksidantlar yoki fermentativ reaksiyalarning kofaktorlari bo'lib, ular asosan oziq-ovqatdan olinadi [11, 13]. Boshqa tomondan, steroid gormonlar organizmning ehtiyojlariga qarab oqsil ishlab chiqarishni sintezlash va bloklash orqali gen ekspressiyasini tartibga soladi. D vitamini o'simlik va hayvon sterollari, fitosterollar va xolesterin fraksiyalarini quyosh nurlari bilan faollashtirish orqali ishlab chiqariladi [5, 10]. Ultrabinafsha nurlar bilan faollashtirilgan o'simlik sterollar D2 vitaminini ishlab chiqaradi. Odamlarda 7-degidroksoxolesterin, asosan terining epidermal qatlamida joylashgan D vitaminining manbasi bo'lib, quyosh nurlari bilan faollashadi va D3 vitamin hosil qiladi so'ngra D vitamini bilan bog'laydigan oqsil bilan bog'lanadi. U jigarga ko'chiriladi, u erda D-25-gidroksilaza vitamini bilan tez gidroksillanadi va D vitaminining asosiy aylanma shakli bo'lgan 25-gidroksivitamin D [25(OH)D] hosil qiladi. bu holatda u 25-gidroksivitamin fermenti tomonidan keyingi gidroksillanish natijasida tug'ma gormonal faolliksiz prohormon hisoblanadi D-1-a-gidroksilaza 25 (OH) D biologik faol shaklga aylanadi – 1,25-dihidroksivitamin d[1,25 (OH)2D]. 1,25-dihidroksivitamin d biologik jarayonlarning keng doirasini boshqaradigan yadro gormoni D vitamini retseptorlari (VRD) bilan bog'lanish orqali to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita 200 dan ortiq turli genlarni tartibga soladi. Katta 25 (OH) D ning 1,25 (OH) 2 D ga aylanishining bir qismi buyraklarda sodir bo'ladi va paratiroid gormoni, kaliy va fosfor darajasi bilan qat'iy tartibga solinadi. Ushbu faollashtirilgan holatda D vitamini klassik endokrin ta'sirga ega qon zardobida va suyak to'qimasida kalsiy metabolizmini tartibga soladi [6, 9, 13]. Ushbu mexanizm orqali D vitamini autokrin va parakrin funksiyalari bilan to'g'ridan-to'g'ri hujayralarga ta'sir qiladi va avtonom nazorat ostida bo'ladi, bu turli endokrin va parakrin funksiyalarning mavjudligi D vitamini nima uchun turli patologik jarayonlarga keng ta'sir qilishini tushuntirishi mumkin [6, 11] VRD lar tanamizning kamida 38 a'zosi va to'qimalarida ishlaydi. Ushbu hayot uchun muxim organlarda VDR hujayra yadrolarida butun inson genomining taxminan 3% transkripsiyasiga ta'sir qiluvchi omil sifatida va plazma membranalarida ko'plab muhim biokimyoviy jarayonlarning gen ifodasi va intensivligi modulyatori sifatida ishlaydi [12,11]. Bilvosita o'zining retseptori orqali vitamin D gormonal faol shakli biologik ta'sirlar kaskadini keltirib chiqarishi mumkin, ular birgalikda inson salomatligiga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatadi [9, 2, 3]. Hozirgi vaqtda olimlar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, D vitamini qo'shimchalarini qabul qilish statistik jihatdan o'tkir respiratorli infeksiyalar bilan kasallanishlar sonini sezilarli darajada pasayishiga olib keldi va kunlik yoki haftalik D vitamini qo'shimchalari o'tkir nafas yo'llari infeksiyasidan himoya qiladi. Shuni ham ta'kidlash kerakki, D vitamini nafaqat homiladorlik paytida, balki uni rejalashtirish paytida ham juda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Reproduktiv tizim bilan bog'liq organlarda, masalan, bachadon, tuxumdonlar, gipofiz bezi va yo'ldoshda vitaminning VDR da mavjudligi, ayolning fertilligiga ta'sirini tasdiqlaydi. Tadqiqotlar shuni isbotladiki D vitamini xayz sikliga va follikulalar yetilishiga, sariq tana rivojlanishida xam ishtirok etadi [3, 4, 15]. Bundan tashqari, D vitamini retseptorlari bilan bog'lanishi CYP19 genining ifodalanishiga ta'sir qiladi, bu esa estrogen sintezida ishtirok etadi. Ba'zi mualliflarning natijalariga ko'ra, gipogonadizm bilan og'riq bemorlarda D vitamini yetishmovchiligining tarqalishi 85% ga yetadi. Shunday qilib, yetishmovchilikni bartaraf etishga qaratilgan terapiya nafaqat gormonal darajani, balki bemorlarning o'zini yaxshi xis qilishiga sezilarli darajada yordam beradi. Bepushtlik bilan davolangan ayollar orasida D vitamini yetishmovchiligining tarqalishi 69% ga yetdi. Shuningdek, turli xil etiologiyali bepushtligi bo'lgan ayollarda xomilador ayollarga nisbatdan D vitamini yetishmovchiligi ko'proq uchraydi [4, 11, 13]. Tuxumdonlar polikistozi sindromi (PCOS) bo'lgan ayollarda D vitamini yetishmovchiligi 85% ni tashkil qiladi. Chet ellik mualliflar metforminni D vitamini va Ca²⁺ bilan birgalikda 6 oy davomida qo'llash normal hayz tsikli va follikulogenezni tiklashga, shuningdek, ayollarda giperandrojeniya bilan bog'liq simptomlarni kamaytirishga yordam berishini isbotladilar

PCOS [4, 2]. Hozirgi vaqtda kalsitriol bu jarayon uchun mas'ul bo'lgan genlarning ifodasini tartibga solish orqali tuxumdonni implantatsiya qilish jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi ma'lum. Bachadon qobig'i hujayralari va plasentalar homiladorlik paytida D vitaminining faol shaklini sintez qiladi, bu esa o'z navbatida homiladorlikni saqlashga qaratilgan immunitet reaksiyasini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shuning uchun homiladorlikni rejalashtirayotgan yoki homiladorlikka tayyorgarlik bosqichida bepushtlikdan aziyat chekayotgan barcha ayollarga qon zardobidagi 25 (OH) D ni aniqlash va uning 30 ng/ml dan yuqori darajasiga erishish orqali D vitamini darajasini baholash tavsiya etiladi [2, 5, 1]. Homiladorlik paytida barcha turdagi vitaminlarga ehtiyoj borligi ma'lum. I va III trimestrlarda 1,25-digidroksivitamin D (1,25(OH) 2D) darajasining oshishini ko'rsatadi, shuning uchun D vitamini almashinuvining buzilishi onaning sog'lig'iga va yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqsalbiy ta'sir qiladi. Asosiy natijalar onaning giperparatiroidizmi, osteomalatsiya, yanggi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda gipokalsemiya, tetaniya, bosh suyagining yuqori qismining ossifikatsiyasi, bosh suyagi va liqildoqlarning kattalashishi [5, 12, 13]. Homiladorlik paytida kalsiy metabolizmi fetoplasental kompleks bilan tartibga solinadi, va bu ikkitasi asosiy maqsadni amalga oshirishga sabab bo'ladi. Ulardan birinchisi skeletni minerallashtirish uchun yetarli miqdorda kalsiy bilan ta'minlash, ikkinchisi esa homila to'qimalari uchun zarur bo'lgan hujayradan tashqari kalsiy miqdorini saqlab qolishdir (inson homilasi odatda 21 g kalsiyni to'playdi va bu kalsiyning 80% III trimestrga to'g'ri keladi) [1, 2, 8]. Kerakli miqdordagi kalsiyni olish va uni tartibga solish uchundarajasi, homila plaseenta, buyraklar, suyak tizimi va onaning ichaklaridan foydalanadi. Shu bilan birga, fetoplasental kompleks onaning tanasidan mustaqil ravishda ishlaydi, hatto onada sezilarli gipokalsemiya va etishmovchilik bo'lsa ham u homila skeletining minerallashtirishda ishtirok etadi va qonda kalsiy miqdorini normal darajada ushlab turadi, shuning uchun kelajakda ona va bolada xar xil kasalliklarni asoratlarini oldini olish uchun onaning qon zardobidagi ushbu vitamin darajasini kuzatib borish juda muhimdir [4, 13].

D vitamini, shuningdek, T va B hujayralarida mavjud bo'lgan yadro VDR va D vitamini faollashtiruvchi fermentlar yordamida adaptiv immunitetda juda muhim rol o'ynaydi. D vitamini mavjud bo'lganda T hujayralari yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarning sekresiyasini oshiradi va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarni ishlab chiqarishga yordam beradi. D vitamini, shuningdek, avtoreaktiv antitelolar ishlab chiqarishni kamaytirish orqali B hujayralarining faollashishi va ko'payishini nazorat qiladi. Bu juda muhim, chunki epidemiologik tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, D vitamini yetishmovchiligi va autoimmun kasalliklarning ko'payishi o'rtasida to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bog'liqlik mavjud. Ushbu kasalliklarning aksariyati, masalan, tarqoq skleroz (MS), Revmatoid artrit (RA), Kron kasalligi va Qandli diabet 1-tip D vitamini yetishmovchiligi bo'lgan bolalarda tez-tez uchraydi [6, 10, 11]. D vitamini, shuningdek, neyroaktiv xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan steroidlarning hosilasi xisoblanadi va miya rivojlanishiga bevosita ta'sir. VDR va 1-a-gidroksilaza miyada keng tarqalgan bo'lib, mahalliy faollashtirilgan D vitamini ishlab chiqarishda ishtirok etadi. Homilada va hayotning dastlabki bosqichlarida D vitaminining yetarli miqdorda bo'lishi miya rivojlanishi va aqliy faoliyati uchun zarur bo'lgan retseptorlarning normal transkripsiya faolligini ta'minlaydi. D vitaminining past darajasi ko'pincha depressiya va og'ir ruhiy kasalliklarga chalingan o'spirinlarda uchraydi. 1980 yildan beri autizm bilan kasallanishning shubhasiz o'sishi kuzatilmoqda, Dunyo bo'ylab xar 160 ta boladan bittasi autizm bilan aziyat chekmoqda, 2016 yilga kelib autizm 8 yoshli bolalarning deyarli 2 % autizm keng tarqalgan (2020 yil). Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, olimlar ushbu kasallik rivojlanishining sabablaridan biri homiladorlik paytida onada D vitamini yetishmovchiligini aniqladilar. Chunki kalsiyning so'rilishidan tashqari, D vitamini ko'plab rivojlanish jarayonlarida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi va ko'plab jinsiy gormonlar faoliyatini nazorat qiladi. Chunki kalsiyning so'rilishidan tashqari, D vitamini ko'plab rivojlanish jarayonlarida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi va ko'plab jinsiy gormonlar faoliyatini nazorat qiladi [5, 10, 12]. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, homiladorlik paytida kemiruvchilarda D vitamini yetishmovchiligi testosteron darajasining oshishiga olib keladi va rivojlanayotgan homila miyasiga jinsiy gormonning ta'siri tufayli autizm xavfini oshayotgani kuzatilgan. Bu testosteronni parchalash uchun zarur bo'lgan fermentning disfunktsiyasi bilan bog'liq [1, 5, 10]. Erkak kalamushlarning rivojlanayotgan miyasida testosteronning ko'payishi kuzatildi, bu ayol homilada topilmadi. Bu bizga autizm spektrining buzilishi nima uchun o'g'il

bolalarda uch baravar tez-tez uchrab turishini tushuntirishga imkon beradi [1, 5, 13]. Hozirgi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, autizm genetika va biokimyoviy moyillikka asoslangan bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu holatga mitoxondriyal disfunktsiya, immunitetning buzilishi, yallig'lanish, oksidlovchi stress va toksiklik orqali autizmning rivojlanishiga turtki beradigan atrof-muhit omillari ta'sir qiladi [18, 22, 25]. Bundan tashqari D vitamini terining ftohimoya qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi, Fotoreportaj-bu ultrabinafsha nurlanishidan kelib chiqqan terining shikastlanishi. Dozaga qarab, ultrabinafsha nurlanish DNKning shikastlanishiga, yallig'lanishiga, hujayra apoptoziga, terining qarishiga va saratonga olib kelishi mumkin [5, 6, 1]. D3 vitaminining sintezi 7-degidroxolesterol konsentratsiyasiga bog'liq bo'lib, u 7-degidroxolesterol reduktaza (DHCR7) faolligiga bog'liq va bu DHCR7 fermenti teridagi D vitamini biosintezini tartibga solishning birinchi qatoridir. Sichqonlarda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, 1,25-digidroksivitamin D3 nurlanishdan oldin yoki keyin teriga mahalliy ravishda surtilgan, D vitamini ftohimoya ta'sirga ega ekanligini isbotlagan [2, 12, 6]. Bir nechta epidemiologik tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, D vitaminining yetarli darajada bo'lishi saraton rivojlanish xavfini va saraton bilan bog'liq o'limni kamaytiradi. Adabiy ma'lumotlar natijalariga ko'ra, olimlar D vitamini buyurishning bosqichma-bosqich sxemasini taklif qilishdi:

1. 4 oygacha bo'lgan bolalarga kuniga 500ME qabul qilish tavsiya etiladi (erta tug'ilganlar uchun-kuniga 800-1000 ME).
2. 4 oydan 4 yilgacha – kuniga 1000 ME.
3. 4 yoshdan 10 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalar – kuniga 1500 ME.
4. 10-16 yosh – kuniga 2000 ME vitaminyil davomida

Shuningdek, olimlar va shifokorlarning fikriga ko'ra, D vitaminining suyuq shakli organizm tomonidan yaxshi so'riladi va bu suvda eriydigan vitamin bo'lib, ko'pchilik shifokorlarning tanlovi hisoblanadi. Uning afzalligi shundaki, u ovqat hazm qilish jarayoniga ta'sir qilmasdan tez va to'liq so'riladi va tabletkalardan farqli o'laroq uzoqroq ta'sir qiladi, chunki bu shaklda xolekalsiferol sekinroq so'riladi. Suyuqlik shakli tabletkaga bilan taqqoslaganda, tanada yetarli miqdorda to'planish uchun ko'proq vaqt kerak bo'ladi [3, 10, 23]. Bundan tashqari D vitaminining haddan tashqari dozasi ko'p ham mumkin, bu vitamin D intoksikatsiyasiga olib keladi bunga ekzogen va endogen yo'llar bilan qabul qilinganligi sabab bo'lishi mumkin.

1. D vitaminining ekzogen intoksikatsiyasi: odatda giperkalsemiya va D vitamini preparatlarining juda yuqori dozalarini qabul qilish natijasida yuzaga kelishi bilan bog'liq.

25-gidroksivitamin D konsentratsiyasi [25 (OH) D]zardobda 150 ng/ml dan yuqori.

2. D vitaminining endogen dozasi oshii ketishi vitamin D – 25(OH)D metabolitlarining ortiqcha ishlab chiqarilishi tufayli rivojlanishi mumkin

va 1,25 (OH)2D:

- granulomatoz kasalliklarda (sarkoidoz, sil, qo'ziqorin kasalliklari va boshqalar) va ba'zi limfomalar;

- bolalarda idiopatik giperkalsemiyasida ushbu metabolitning degradatsiyasining pasayishi tufayli;

– Uilyams-Beren sindromi kabi tug'ma kasalliklarda;

– tavsiya etilgan va xavfsiz deb hisoblangan dozalarda ham D vitamini qabul qilish bilan bog'liq simptomsiz giperkalsemiya-tamin vitamini metabolizmini tartibga solishda D vitaminiga yuqori sezuvchanlik-Uilyams sindromi

Haddan tashqari D vitamini juda xavfli ta'sirga ega, bu siydik tizimining disfunktsiyasi bilan giperkalsemiya, yumshoq to'qimalarda, buyraklarda, jigarda, o'pkada va qon tomirlarida ortiqcha kalsiy to'planishi bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, berilgan vitamin qon bosimiga xam ta'sir qiladi, bu fonda kardiopatiya va kardionevroz rivojlanadi. Shuning uchun shifokorlar bemorning qonidagi D vitaminining asl tarkibiga e'tibor berishlari kerak.

Xulosa: D vitamini bilan yetarli darajada ta'minlash har qanday yoshdagi odamlarning sog'lig'ini saqlash uchun juda muhimdir. Chunki D vitamini mushak-skelet tizimiga ta'siridan tashqari, hozirgi vaqtda u immunitet, ruhiy salomatlik va aholining umumiy umrini saqlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

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9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

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